

CLASSIFICATION, CLINIC, DIAGNOSIS AND CLAIM PRINCIPLES OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS ACCORDING TO THE FORM OF BRONCHITIS

Rakhmatov Jasurbek Khurshid o'g'li

Samarkand State medical University Faculty of Pediatrics

iphonejasur721@icloud.com

Uroqova Marjona Shamsiddinovna

Samarkand State medical University Faculty of Pediatrics

uroqovamarjona1026@gmail.com

Anvarov Navro'zbek Anvar o'g'li

Samarkand State medical University Faculty of Pediatrics

anvarovnavruz98@gmail.com

Murtozoyeva Ug'iloy Saydulla qizi

Samarkand State medical University Faculty of Pediatrics

ogiloymurtazoyava@gmail.com

Annotation: *On this basis, a classification project was presented in terms of finding realistic approaches to primary prevention of features of chronic bronchitis stages. At the Lamb stage of this disease, a large proportion of viral and related infections have been identified. A schematic diagram of etiological and patho-genetic treatment is presented. In this article we can discuss information about classification, clinic, diagnosis and claim principles of etiopathogenesis according to form of bronchitis.*

Keywords: Bronchitis, types of bronchitis, methods of treatment, signs, symptoms of the disease, observation of patients, prevention.

Etiology of bronchitis. In children, pure bacterial bronchitis is rare, calling the disease mainly respiratory viruses. But the activation of bacteria under the

influence of viruses is common, and the disease is often called by staphylococci, Streptococci, Pneumococci from bacteria. In bronchitis, addiction to the disease plays an important role. Because of these, some children suffer more from bronchitis than others. Bronchitis is the usual clinical picture of some children's infectious diseases, including measles, whooping cough. Bronchitis classification: 1. Acute simple bronchitis. 2.Acute obstructive bronchitis. 3.Acute bronchiolitis 4.Acute obliterated bronchiolitis. 5.Relapsed bronchitis. 6.Relapsed obstructive bronchitis. 7.Chronic bronchitis: primary, secondary. 8.Chronic bronchiolitis.

Pathogenesis: Disease is the main sign, developed under the influence of ORVI, is an obstruction of the respiratory tract. Bronchi mucous membranes swell, the walls thicken, glandular hypersecretion is observed, they accumulate on the surface and walls of the bronchi, narrowing the surface of small, medium and large-caliber bronchi, as a result of which the release of a pleasant breath is heard from a long distance. Air accumulation in the lungs leads to functional emphysema. Alveolar ventilation of the lungs is impaired, oxygenation of the blood decreases, hypoxia, hypoxemia develops.

Chronic bronchitis is characterized by a cough with sputum, mainly in the morning. The severity of the cough can be different, from minor to very high. Sputum is initially colorless or grayish, then becomes light yellow or yellow, its amount also varies greatly. Exacerbation of the disease occurs, as a rule, after a viral infection of the respiratory tract suffered "on the feet", since the virus weakens the body's defenses (the immune system). During an exacerbation, patients note weakness, bruising, malaise, the appearance of wheezing in the chest, difficulty breathing is possible.

The diagnosis of chronic bronchitis, as a rule, is established on the basis of the characteristic symptoms of the disease and their duration, which, together with the examination and physical examination data, make it possible to prescribe adequate treatment.

Additional diagnostic methods (a general blood test with an assessment of the leukocyte formula, ESR, a study of the level of C-reactive protein, a general sputum analysis, bacteriological examination of sputum with determination of sensitivity to antibiotics, as well as chest X-ray and spirometry) are necessary to exclude other respiratory diseases (pneumonia, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, etc.), as well as when deciding on the appointment of antibiotics.

Other studies (computed tomography of the chest organs, bronchoscopy, esophagogastroduodenoscopy) are carried out only in cases where there are doubts about the diagnosis. It is fundamentally important to give up smoking — the leading factor in the progression of structural changes in the bronchi and the transition of chronic bronchitis to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

The signal of the onset of exacerbation is not so much cough and sputum discharge (although they tend to intensify, and sputum acquires a yellowish or greenish hue), as the appearance of weakness, feelings of malaise, fatigue, sweating, and an increase in body temperature. It is these symptoms that are considered a reason to consult a doctor and start active therapeutic measures.

Conclusion. Since any exacerbation of chronic bronchitis has an adverse effect on the condition of the bronchi and the general course of the disease, prevention of exacerbations is of particular importance in the treatment. In addition to restorative measures (proper nutrition, hardening of the body, reasonable physical activity), it is important to avoid hypothermia, stressful situations, communication with people with acute respiratory diseases. It is also possible to prevent infection with viruses with the help of a medical mask, frequent ventilation of premises and washing hands with soap.

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